

**Citation for the Presentation of the 2017
ICPE Medal to**

**Professor Marco Antonio Moreira
Brazil**

**at GIREP-ICPE-EPEC Conference, Dublin,
Ireland
July 2017**

Professor Marco Antonio Moreira is awarded the ICPE Medal for 2017 in recognition of his sustained efforts in physics education.

Marco Antonio Moreira graduated from the University of Rio Grande do Sul in 1965 and started his career as a High School Teacher of Physics and Mathematics. In 1967 he became a faculty member of Institute of Physics, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, becoming Professor of Physics Education in 1987. In between, he went to the Physics Department of Cornell University as a Visiting Fellow in 1972 and was awarded a Ph. D from Cornell in Science Education in 1977.

He has been a member of the Council on Inter-American Conferences on Physics Education since 1986, serving as President from 1994 to 1997. From 1996 to 1999 he was also the Chair of the Commission of Specialists in Physics Education of the Brazilian Ministry of Education. Since 1987 Professor Moreira has been a member of the Consulting Board, *Enseñanza de las Ciencias*, Barcelona, Spain and since 1988 Co-Chair of the International Ph.D. Program in Science Education, University of Burgos, Spain.

Professor Moreira was a pioneer of physics education research in Latin America. During his half-century career in physics education, he has written 56 books, organized 12 proceedings, contributed 260 papers to scientific journals and 126 papers to international meetings. Most of these are in physics, or science, education, theories of learning, educational research, teaching methodology in higher education, and epistemology. More than a hundred students have completed their Theses and Dissertations under the supervision of Professor Moreira. Many of his former students are now working in universities in Brazil, Latin America, and other countries around the world.

Today the International Commission on Physics Education takes great pleasure in recognizing Professor Moreira's extraordinary contribution to Physics Education in Latin America, and, naturally, all over the world.

Hideo Nitta
ICPE Chair